

The Strength of Aligned Short-Fiber Carbon, Glass, and Hybrid Carbon/Glass Composites

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ABSTRACT

A statistical model of failure accounts for the good translation of strength from continuous fiber to short carbon fiber composites. Measurements of the mechanical properties of glass and carbon/glass hybrid short-fiber composites show that microstructural damage occurs at relatively low loads.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Highly-aligned short-fiber composites can now be produced by the centrifuge [1] and vacuum [2] processes which perform the alignment by flow of a suspension medium containing the fibers. Typically carbon and/or glass fibers of about 3mm length are aligned into felts and are subsequently impregnated with a thermoset resin system. The materials have applications in the molding of parts with complex curvatures and changes of section thickness where the ability of the uncured pre-preg to elongate both parallel and perpendicular to the fiber direction without splitting complements the predominantly shear deformation of woven materials [3]. The high degree of fiber alignment ensures good translation of fiber stiffness and strength into the short fiber composite.

Besides their structural applications these materials are an interesting model system in which to investigate the role of both the fiber-end stress concentrations and the non-uniformity of fiber strength in determining the overall properties of a composite. Recent practical and theoretical work on mixed fiber or hybrid composites [4,5] has indicated that the effective strength of a low elongation fiber may be enhanced when it is combined with a higher elongation fiber, e.g., carbon with glass. The effect has been explained in terms of the statistics and energetics of fiber failure, and modification of the stress concentrations within the composite. In all cases it is expected to be most pronounced when the two types of fiber are intimately mixed. Such a degree of dispersion is difficult to achieve with continuous fibers, but can be obtained relatively easily by the short-fiber alignment processes.

In this paper we compare predictions of composite strength from a probabilistic model (which incorporates the non-uniformity of fiber strength) with experimental measurements on carbon, glass, and hybrid composites.

Failure Mechanism

The strengths of both carbon and glass reinforcing fibers are limited by internal and surface defects and typically have a coefficient of variation of about 15-25%. When a unidirectional continuous fiber composite is loaded fibers initially fail at random thereby locally overstressing neighbouring fibers. Groups of fiber fractures accumulate until one becomes sufficiently large to cause catastrophic failure. Such a group of fiber fractures represents a 'weakest-link' within the structure, and in this sense the failure may be termed 'brittle'. A chain-of-bundles model is commonly applied to this failure mechanism [5,6,7]. The composite is considered to be a series of 'slices' (or short bundles) which are statistically independent; failure of any one represents failure of the composite. The strength distribution of such a composite is readily obtained from the strength distribution of the slices by applying weakest-link scaling since all slices must survive at a given stress if the composite as a whole is to survive. However, determining the strength distribution of the slices from the fiber strength distribution and geometry of the system is a particularly complex problem when load is re-distributed locally [6]. Various exact and approximate approaches have been developed for simple geometrical arrangements of fibers. In an attempt to overcome the limitations in geometry, number of fibers, and load re-distribution the failure process has been simulated by Monte Carlo methods. The general limitation to this approach is the rather small size of composite (and probability of survival) which can be accommodated within realistic constraints on computer time and memory. However it is relatively easy to model short-fiber and hybrid composites as presented in this and a previous paper [7].

Strength and Variability of Fibers

A single batch of both Hercules AS-4 carbon fiber and of E-glass fiber were used throughout, and their strengths were approximated by simple two-parameter Weibull distributions. The probability of survival of a fiber of length L is given by

$$P_s = \exp \left(-L \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^w \right) \quad (1)$$

where σ_0 and w are the scale and shape parameter respectively, and σ is the fiber stress. The scatter in fiber strength is determined solely by the shape parameter w which is approximately the inverse of the coefficient of variation, and since this plays an important role in determining the fracture mechanism and variability of the composite we have measured it in several ways.

The strengths of a number of single fibers of fixed length were ranked in order to obtain a cumulative distribution corresponding to equation (1). Plotting on appropriate logarithmic axes gave the shape parameter w .

The mean strength of the Weibull distribution is

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_0} = L^{-w} \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{w} \right) \quad (2)$$

and w was obtained by plotting the variation of mean fiber strength with length on logarithmic axes. Similarly, the mean strength of loose bundles of fiber shows the same variation of strength with length, and this test was performed on loose bundles of carbon and glass fibers.

Under displacement controlled loading a loose fiber bundle produces a load elongation curve which passes through a maximum. If it is assumed that the fibers are linear elastic to fracture and are of equal diameter and modulus, the proportion surviving at any given strain is indicated by the ratio of actual load to the projected linear portion of the curve. In this way an approximation to the strength distribution is obtained, and by plotting it on logarithmic axes w may be found from the gradient.

Table 1	FIBER VARIABILITY	AS-4	E-glass
		<u>w</u>	<u>w</u>
Single fiber mean strength vs. length		11.3	-
Single fiber strength distribution		4.3	-
Loose bundle mean strength vs. length		4.7	4.0
Loose bundle strength distribution		5.3	3.2
Single fiber multiple fracture		4.6	-

Fig. 1 Tensile test results on a common strain axis. (a) Load strain curve for all-glass short fiber composite showing decrease in stiffness, and hysteresis in a single loading cycle to 1% strain. (Subsequently strained to failure)

Acoustic emission rate curves for (a) short glass-fiber composite (b) 80:20 short glass: carbon fiber (c) 90:10 short glass: carbon hybrid, (d) continuous carbon fiber composite.

Table 2 PERCENTAGE CHANGE IN STIFFNESS

Composite:	E-glass	glass/carbon hybrids	carbon
		90:10	80:20
	-21.8	-12.5	+12.8

The distribution of fiber lengths at a range of stresses will also yield a value of w . This method was used to obtain w for single carbon fibers which were bonded to a substrate and strained so as to induce multiple fractures. (A correction was made for the length of fiber which was not fully stressed close to fiber fractures.)

Estimates of w from all these methods are similar and are summarized in Table 1. In every case the results showed deviations from true Weibull behavior, but the two-parameter approximation was retained for its simplicity and convenience in subsequent analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fabrication

Aligned continuous, short-fiber, and hybrid materials were autoclave molded into 0.5 mm thick plates which were cut into 12.5 x 150 mm parallel-sided coupons. The root-mean-square fiber mis-orientation in these plates was determined by optical microscopy to be 6.8° in the plane of lamination, and 2.4° perpendicular to that plane in the case of the short-fiber materials, and essentially nil for the continuous fiber composite. The volume fraction of fiber was approximately 45% in Ciba Geigy Fiberdux 914 modified epoxy resin (cured 1 hour at 120°C and 2 hours at 175°C).

Tensile Testing and Failure Mode

Coupon specimens were strained to failure at a rate of approximately 10^{-4} per second while the rate of acoustic emission was monitored simultaneously. None of the composites was perfectly linearly-elastic, but all exhibited sudden and catastrophic failure. The short fiber glass and 90:10 glass: carbon hybrid specimens typically failed by a combination of fracture across their width and longitudinal splitting at a shallow angle $\sim 30^\circ$ to the specimen axes. In contrast the 80:20 glass: carbon short-fiber hybrid and continuous carbon fiber composites failed by propagation of a fracture directly across the specimen width. The continuous carbon composite showed an increase in modulus with loading whereas the short fiber composites all showed progressive decreases which were higher with increasing glass fiber content. Table 2 gives the difference between the modulus at failure and the initial modulus.

Figure 1 shows that this change in stiffness for a short-glass fiber composite occurs below 1% strain, and that it is associated with a permanent elongation of the specimen by only about 0.02% strain. Only the continuous carbon fiber composite was fully elastic. This difference is also reflected in the rate of acoustic emission which was approximately 3 to 7 times higher for the short-fiber composites. The onset of acoustic emission roughly corresponded with the change in stiffness.

Figure 2 presents the secant modulus to failure, failure stress, and failure strain of the composites corrected to a fiber volume fraction of 100%. While the modulus follows the rule-of-mixtures, strength and failure strain do not. Dashed tie lines indicate a change in failure mode, or join points for continuous and short-fiber composites.

MODELLING OF STRENGTH

Monte Carlo Simulations

A slice of composite was simulated by a square array of 100 fibers of length δ and random strength given by a two-parameter Weibull distribution. The computational procedure located the weakest fiber in the array and re-distributed its load onto the four nearest neighbours if these had not failed. The matrix contribution to strength was ignored. This process was repeated until all fibers had failed and the maximum applied load was recorded as the strength. The results of 100 simulations were ranked to obtain cumulative distributions. This approach, and results for continuous fiber composites are described in greater detail in [7].

Fig. 2 Experimentally measured mechanical properties as a function of composition. Open symbols represent short-fiber composites.

Fig. 3 Predicted strengths of 100-fiber composites scaled to the strength of a composite reinforced with fibers of uniform strength equal to 1. Bold line indicates continuous fiber, fine lines are for short fiber composites.

The same model has been extended to simulate discontinuous and hybrid composites. The geometry of a short-fiber composite was approximated by randomly specifying a proportion β of the fibers in a slice to have zero strength, and re-distributing the load as described above. Strictly this procedure represents a composite with a near-exponential distribution of fiber length since a composite with fibers of constant length would have a periodic structure if the fiber end were butted together. For the purpose of modelling a real short-fiber composite it is not unrealistic to assume a random distribution of butted fiber ends, and in this case the constant β represents the ratio of slice thickness δ to fiber length L .

$$\beta = \frac{\delta}{L} \quad (3)$$

Hybrids were modelled by randomly mixing two populations of fibers having different strengths. Designating these A and B, they may be related in four ways: (i) B stronger and less variable than A, (ii) B weaker and more variable, (iii) B stronger and more variable, and (iv) B weaker and less variable. In cases (i) and (ii) the cumulative distributions intersect. (Cases (i) and (iii) and (iv) are distinct because A and B may differ in stiffness) Within experimental limitations our measurements have not shown a great difference between the variabilities of glass and carbon fiber, and in the simulations they have been made equal. The re-distribution of load is complicated by the fact that the two types of fiber have different moduli (and diameters). At a given strain the load carried by a fiber is proportional to its stiffness (product of cross-sectional area and modulus) and when it failed this load was re-distributed onto the four nearest neighbours in proportion to their stiffnesses. Thus each neighbor experienced an equal strain increment given by the load carried by the failed fiber divided by the sum of the stiffnesses of the neighbours. The glass fiber was defined to have 0.333 of the stiffness and 0.6 of the strength of the carbon fiber, and both had a Weibull shape parameter of 5.

Fig. 4 Predicted relative strengths of hybrid continuous (solid line) and short-fiber (dashed line) composites, scaled to the strength of the carbon fiber composite.

Results of Simulations

Previous simulations of continuous fiber composites [7] are in good agreement with alternative approaches to the problem and can be summarized as follows:

- (i) The strength of the composite decreases as the variability of the fiber is increased.
- (ii) The variability of the composite increases only marginally for relatively large increases of the variability of the fiber.
- (iii) The size of the critical group of fiber fractures which precipitates failure is larger when the fibers are more variable, and is approximately equal to the ratio of fiber to composite variability.

Very similar results were obtained for short-fiber composites although their strengths were lower. Figure 3 compares the predicted strengths of continuous and short-fiber 'slices' containing fibers of different variabilities. However, a composite of realistic size is composed of many slices and its strength must be calculated by weakest-link scaling of the strength distribution of the slices. If the variabilities of the systems modelled differ their strengths scale differently with the size of the composite. Therefore, the ranking of strengths at the 'slice' level may not be preserved at the composite level. The coefficients of variation of continuous and short-fiber composites in fact show little difference and within the limitations of the model composites of larger size can be expected to exhibit the same relative strengths.

Figure 4 shows that the predicted relative strengths of the hybrid composites are below those expected from a simple rule-of-mixtures. (Again the variabilities of the slices are virtually identical). The short-fiber hybrids are marginally weaker.

DISCUSSION

The overall objective of this work is to compare predictions of strength with experimental results. In concept it is possible to predict the absolute strength of continuous and short-fiber composites from the computed strength distributions. However, this requires that the length δ be known with considerable accuracy. While it may be estimated from microscopic observations to be about 100 μm [5] the uncertainty is several times this amount. Therefore, the predictions are most useful as comparisons between short-fiber and continuous composites in which δ is assumed to be the same. Unfortunately difficulties in the supply of experimental materials have prevented us from making the comparison with either glass or carbon fiber. However, previously published work [1] suggests that the strength translation from continuous to short-fiber carbon fiber composites is about 91%, and thus agrees reasonably well with our prediction of 96%. (Fig. 3, fiber shape parameter assumed to be 7) The experimental results is probably somewhat lower on account of the small degree of misalignment of the short fibers.

The short glass fiber and 90:10 hybrid composites are significantly weaker than the 80:20 hybrid whereas their modulus follows the rule-of-mixtures. We attribute this to the different failure mode which involves shear splitting. It is unlikely that this glass-rich end of the binary hybrid system will show such a good translation of strength (or agreement with the model) as the carbon end.

The higher level of acoustic emission from all the short fiber composites, their non-linear stress/strain curves, and their hysteresis in cyclic loading suggest that substantial microstructural damage occurs above roughly half the strain to failure. At low strain the majority of this is unlikely to be fiber breakage since the phenomena are not observed with continuous fiber composites. Although not confirmed, it is probable that matrix cracking and fiber/matrix debonding occur. In the hybrid systems there is a complex state of residual stress on account of the thermal expansion mismatch between the glass and fiber, and this and other microstructural aspects are the subject of continued study. It is interesting that the level of acoustic emission (at equal strain)

is consistently higher for the two hybrids than for the pure glass and pure carbon composites which suggests that internal stress may be an important factor.

The decrease in curvature (lower stiffness at higher strain) of the short fiber composites with higher carbon fiber content reflects the strain-stiffening of the fiber itself, and perhaps also the better matrix bond to carbon fiber. In these short-fiber composites microstructural processes cause significant changes of the mechanical properties at much lower strains than is the case with continuous fiber reinforcement, and this may have implications for long term durability.

CONCLUSIONS

A statistical model of composite strength accurately predicts high translation of continuous fiber composite strength to short-carbon-fiber composites which fail by fiber-to-fiber fracture. In this case the model predicts relative insensitivity to fiber length.

Shear failure is more in evidence with short glass fiber composites and hybrids with a high glass fiber content, and their strength may be more dependent on the small degree of fiber misorientation.

All short-fiber composites showed evidence of microstructural damage above roughly half their failure strain. *no 2*

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